

An exploration of spin states in nanoparticle structures

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Multireference calculations of nanoparticle structures of metals and metal oxides consider the electron spin states. The electronic ground state configuration of a metal nanoparticle, e.g. an Au or Ag nanoparticle consists of electron spin states arising off a large number of metal atoms connected to each other with covalent bonds. The spherical metal nanoparticles of 1 to 2 nm size are constructed from their crystallographic unit cells and the local symmetry is preserved in the final spherical nanoparticle structures. The electronic structure properties of nanoparticles may depend on the size and shape (Wulff, sphere) of the nanoparticle and can be examined in single reference calculations where only the lowest total spin is considered in the calculation, however, in multireference calculations we can ensure an accurate description of the electronic structure of open shell systems and strong electron correlation. A comparison between single reference and multireference calculations is shown.